

MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH - TWO FOLK DILBANDI

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Annotation: this article provides information about the life and work of Maqsud Shaikhzoda. Adib's writings, his books, have been widely interpreted in this very article.

Keywords: poet, work, Maqsud Shaykhzade, book, poem, Tashkent.

Shaikhzoda stood out from all of us not only in the sense of reason, but also in the sense of siymo. The idle question of the autonomous mouth did not seem to melt into it. On the contrary, everywhere, all the time, in all environments and conditions, the feeling of pride, which has made his heart prosperous, has been exasperated. He leaned, even proud, and said that he was Azerbaijani, coming from Azerbaijan. While reciting the same words, Maqsud's face seemed as if the sun in the sky had moved. One of the outstanding exponents of Uzbek literature, the famous poet, zabardast playwright, literary scholar and translator Maqsud Shaykhzadeh was born in 1908 in the city of Oqtosh, Azerbaijan.

After receiving his primary and secondary education in Aktaş, he studied abstractly at the Baku higher Pedagogical Institute, and from 1925 he worked as a teacher in the city of Darband.

Shaykhzoda came to Tashkent in 1928, served as an associate professor at the editorial offices of various newspapers and magazines, and in 1935-1938 at the Institute of language and literature under the committee of Sciences, and from 1938 until the end of his life at the Department of Uzbek classical literature of the Nizami Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute (now University). The poet's literary career began in 1929. The publication of his collections "ten poems" (1932), "my consonants" (1933), "the third book" (1934), "the Republic" (1934) signaled the arrival of a poet with a distinctive voice in literature.

Shaykhzoda's tragedy "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" (1944), written during the years of World War II, historically accurately and insults the martial courage of the last Khwarazmian King, whom karshi fought for the freedom and independence of his land to the Mughal conquerors. During these years, the poet mobilized all his creative energy, the temperature of his soul, to the victory that would be gained over the enemy. From the first days of the war, the "fight nechun?", which glorifies the heroes of the battle, expresses the selfless work of those behind the front?" (1941), "battle and song" (1942), his poetic collections such as "the heart says...", the historical drama "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" (1944), and a number of other publicist works.

Maqsud Shaykhzoda made his poetic collections about the struggle for peace in the post-war years, such as "the notebook of fifteen years", "my applause", "the ToRs of The Times", "The Devil", "The Lord of the quarter century".

The fiery poet mustabid did not stay away from the oppression of the regime. He was first imprisoned in 1928 and sentenced to 3 years in exile in Uzbekistan on charges of anti-Soviet agitation. For the second time, Shaikhzoda was removed from the Union of writers of Uzbekistan, imprisoned on September 22, 1952 and sentenced to 25 years in prison.

The poet gained freedom after the death of Stalin; returning to creativity, in 1958, Kohna and navqiron wrote the lyrical epic "Tashkent", dedicated to the city of Tashkent. In 1960, he wrote the tragedy" Mirzo Ulugbek", in which he created the image of the great astrologer and enlightened statesman Mirzo Ulugbek.

Shaykhzoda turned Pushkin's "copper rider", Lermontov's "prisoner of the Caucasus", Mayakovsky's "very neat" epics and many poems, Shakespeare's tragedies and sonnets "Hamlet", "Romeo and Juliet", poems by Nozim Hikmat, works of Azerbaijani poets into Uzbek.

In his poetic work, shaykhzoda shook kalam, mainly on modern topics, and in his drama, he gave a fresh artistic life to the siymos and events that help to shed light on the modern problems in it, giving a thoughtful look at the historical utmish. He wrote the sunggi stage play about Beruniy during the sunggi years of his life.

The scientific work of shaykhzadeh on the history of Uzbek literature, Uzbek folk oral creativity, in particular the research of Alisher Navoi creativity, is also noteworthy. Shaykhzoda, not only writing works in all types and genres of fiction, has also been prolific as a literary scholar and critic. As early as 1941, the monograph" the Genial poet " was published by Sh. until the last days of his life, Navoi was constantly engaged in his life and work. After the article "on the lyrical

hero of Navoi" (1948), which he wrote on the occasion of the 500th anniversary of Navoi, he created major scientific studies "on some poetic methods of Navoi lyricism" (1959), "in the Art Room of the Master" (3-part article, 1965-66), "the Sultan of the ghazal estate" (1966), "from the history of The poet died in Tashkent in 1967.

Maqsud Shaykhzoda was also a candidate of philological Sciences, Associate Professor. But above all he was a great poet. Adib's works have been translated into many sister and foreign languages.

In 2001, for his outstanding contribution to the development of Uzbek literature and culture, Shaykhzoda was awarded the order of Merit.

But in our recent history there is such a person who, not looking at being a representative of a foreign country, only after living in Tashkent for a year, learns the Uzbek language and mentors in an ordinary school. Not Shugina, she later enrolled in the Faculty of Oriental Studies at the Central Asian State University. These years set the stage for a deeper understanding of the charm of the Uzbek language and a more perfect study of the language. Over the years, he has grown to become a classical Uzbek poet. The most notable aspect is that, although he himself was of Azerbaijani nationality, he made a contribution to the development of this language by creating it in Uzbek. The happiness of feeling that he is the child of Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan, the great honor of falling into the eyes of both hands, must have been written on his forehead.

The Uzbek people's writer Shukrullo called Shaykhzoda "Shakespeare of Uzbek literature". After all, his great services for the Uzbek language – translations of Uzbek works into Azeri, Russian and Azeri works into Uzbek, Uzbek prose works, poems and epics-deserve this definition. Maqsud Shaykhzoda siyma has become a symbol of friendship, brotherhood, enlightenment, spirituality, goodness for the peoples of Uzbekistan and Azerbaijan, and will continue to be so further.

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